

NURTURING ADOLESCENTS ABILITY TO IDENTIFY, UNDERSTAND AND RESOLVE CONFLICT WITH SELF FOR POSITIVE MENTAL HEALTH

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Abstract: The self is a system of interrelated parts that collects, evaluates, and reacts to information about oneself. It consists of mechanisms that generate information, standards by which this information is made meaningful and relevant, and a reactive system whereby the information is experienced on “embodied”. Self-concept represents how a person sees himself or herself and is thought to have three components: ideal self (the person one would like to be); public self (the image one believes others have of oneself); and real self (the sum of those subjective thoughts, feelings, and needs that a person sees as being authentically theirs). An adolescent’s self identity generally focuses on simple characteristics, such as physical appearance, perception of self by peers, etc along with abstract and multifaceted ideas. Sometimes there is a conflict between the different components of self resulting in anxiety, which often leads an adolescent to take extreme steps, such as turning to drugs, alcohol, attempting suicide, running away from home etc. To nurture good mental health, adolescents should be guided to have a healthy sense of self and self-esteem which can improve all areas of their life.

Therefore the present study was taken up to assess the adolescent’s ability to identify, understand and resolve conflicts with self and study the influence of an intervention program in nurturing positive self concept and self-esteem. A pre test post test method was adopted, with an experimental and control group, having a sample of 54 and 46 in the experimental and control group respectively, for the current study along with an intervention programme aimed at guiding adolescents to identify, understand and resolve conflict with self which would lead to a positive mental health.

Index Terms - Conflict with self, Adolescence, self concept, self esteem, positive mental health.

I. INTRODUCTION

The search for identity which Erikson defined as a coherent conception of the self, made up of goals, values, and beliefs to which the person is solidly committed, comes into focus during adolescence. Adolescent’s cognitive development enables them to construct a “theory of self” (Elkind, 1998).

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Conflicts are an inevitable part of life. They reflect the complex and sometimes inconsistent wants values and expectations of individuals and groups. Often the causes of conflicts at adolescence are more mental than physical. A bad relationship, poor self image, a history of abuse, stress, frustration and many other factors can change their overall attitude towards life which may directly impede their overall concept of self.

When conflict with self is poorly managed it has a negative impact on adolescent's relationships and on their self-esteem. However, nurturing in adolescents the skills for resolving conflict can help significantly. By learning to manage conflicts effectively adolescents will be much happier and have better intrapersonal attitudes. This will in turn lead to a positive mental health and well being of adolescents.

II. OBJECTIVES:

- To develop an appropriate scale to assess the adolescents' ability to identify, understand and resolve conflict with self.
- To help adolescents identify, understand and resolve conflict with self through nurturing the development of skills in adolescents to resolve conflicts with self.
- To develop appropriate modules for imparting skills in identifying, understanding and resolving conflict with self.

III. HYPOTHESIS:

1. Adolescents do not have the ability to identify, understand and resolve conflict with self.
2. Nurturing the development of conflict resolution skills in adolescents will not help them in resolving conflict with self.

IV. METHODOLOGY:

Phase 1: Development of Tools

The researcher developed the CIUR Scale (conflict identification, understanding and resolving scale) consisting of three parts. Part A, assessed the adolescents ability to identify and resolve conflict with self and has 10 items, with close ended statements. Part B assesses the adolescents' conflict resolution pattern and has 10 items which are open ended. Part C consists of a hypothetical situation with both open and closed ended questions to assess the adolescents' ability to identify, understand and resolve conflict.

Phase 2: Identification of Schools

A survey of the different schools in Bangalore city, which would be open to this experimental study for one whole academic year as a part of its curriculum was carried out. Two schools were identified viz., 'The Titan School', Hosur for carrying out the experimental design of the research study, and 'JSS Public School, Bangalore as the control School.

Phase 3: Identification of samples

176 samples were drawn to standardize the conflict resolution pattern scale developed by the researchers. The developed tool has reliability of 0.901 derived using split-half method.

For the pre-post experimental design in the study 100 early adolescents aged 12-13 yrs studying in 7th standard from the schools selected were identified. The experimental group consisted of 54 participants while the control group consisted of 46 participants.

Phase 4: Pre-test data collection

The developed CIUR Scale was administered to the experimental and control group.

Phase 5: Development of training modules

Based on inputs received from the pre-test data and discussions held with experts in the field, the researcher developed modules to nurture in adolescents the ability to identify, understand and resolve conflict. Modules were designed in such a way that the adolescents were first taught how to identify and understand conflict, and then it was followed by teaching appropriate resolution strategies. The modules were activity based.

Phase 6: Intervention programme

The developed modules were introduced to adolescents over a period of one whole academic year.

Phase 7: Post-test.

After the end of the academic year the CIUR Scale was re-administered to both the groups for post-test data collection.

Phase 8: Statistical analysis of data

Descriptive statistical analysis was carried out in the present study. Significance was assessed at 1 % level of significance. Student t test (two tailed, independent) was used to find the significance of study parameters. P values were obtained by paired proportion test.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

table 1: socio demographic variables

Sl.No	Socio-demographic variables	Experimental group (n=54)		Control group (n=46)	
		No	%	No	%
I	Age in years				
1.	11 years	0	0.0	4	8.7
2.	12 years	22	40.7	35	76.1
3.	13 years	28	51.9	7	15.2
4.	14 years	4	7.4	0	0.0
II	Gender				
1.	Male	23	42.6	23	50.0
2.	Female	31	57.4	23	50.0
III	Religion				
1.	Hindu	49	90.7	46	100.0
2.	Muslim	3	5.6	0	0.0
3.	Christian	2	3.7	0	0.0
IV	Type of family				
1.	Nuclear	52	96.3	37	80.4
2.	Joint	2	3.7	9	19.6
V	Monthly Income in Rupees				
1.	5000 or less	3	5.6	0	0.0
2.	5001-10000	2	3.7	1	2.2
3.	10001-15000	11	20.4	5	10.9
4.	>15000	38	70.4	40	87.0

It can be inferred from the table that a majority of the respondents in the experimental group (51.9%) belong to the age group of 13 years, whereas a majority of respondents from control group (76.1%) belong to the age group of 12 years. Majority of the respondents follow the Hindu religion, come from nuclear families and have a monthly income of more than rupees 15,000 in both the experimental and control group.

table 2: comparison of the adolescents' ability to identify, understand and resolve conflict with self in the pre and post assessment

Sl.No	Identifying and Understanding conflicts	Experimental group (n=54)	Control group (n=46)	P value
1.	Pre-assessment	14.19±5.03	13.43±6.95	0.534
2.	Post –assessment	12.48±6.67	14.17±5.96	0.188
3.	% Change	12.05%	-5.51%	-
4.	P value	0.121	0.227	-
Sl.No	Resolving Conflicts	Experimental group (n=54)	Control group (n=46)	P value
1.	Pre-assessment	15.83±3.23	21.41±6.71	<0.001**
2.	Post –assessment	21.70±5.34	23.00±5.25	0.226
3.	% Change	37.08	7.46%	-
4.	P value	<0.001**	0.162	-

Adolescence is a critical period in development for acquiring societal contribution values, because it involves the transition between childhood—characterized by strong dependency on parents and caregivers—to adulthood, in which one is expected to function as a mature, independent individual (e.g., politically, financially, and socially) and to commit to social norms (Crone & Dahl 2012, Duell et al. 2016). Self-perspectives are critically involved in identity development. Identity development is often described as the search for self-defined values and commitments to various domains of life (education, work, social relationships) (Becht et al. 2017a). It was hypothesized that Adolescents do not have the ability to identify, understand and resolve conflict with self. The pre-assessment data of the experimental and control group indicate that this assumption is right. To support this, prior longitudinal research including daily assessment of identity processes (reconsideration of goals, exploration in depth, and commitment to goals) showed that a subgroup of adolescents (approximately 50%) develops an identity crisis in either the educational or interpersonal domains (higher reconsideration with relatively low or vague commitments), with dips in commitment around ages 15–17 (Becht et al. 2016). [Crocetti et al. (2016) finds a similar dip in self-concept clarity around ages 17–18.] A study on evaluation of self-traits reported that adolescents show a reduction in positive self-descriptions in the academic domain around ages 14–16 (van der Crujisen et al. 2018), which also supports that adolescents are not able to fully identify, understand and resolve conflicts with self. After the intervention program, a significant difference is observed between the experimental and control group data in the post assessment. Therefore, it can be concluded that adolescents need to be trained in identifying, understanding and resolving conflicts with self for nurturing positive mental health.

table 3: assessment of the influence of intervention program through simulated conflict situations:

table 3a: assessment of the adolescent's ability to identify the type of conflict

Sl.No	Type of conflict	Pre-assessment	Post-assessment	% change	P value
I	Experimental group				
1.	Conflict with friends	1(1.9%)	0	-1.9%	0.1558
2.	Conflict with self	48(88.9%)	53(98.1%)	9.3%	0.3111
3.	Conflict in school	3(5.6%)	1(1.9%)	-3.7%	0.1601
4.	Conflict with parents	1(1.9%)	0	-1.9%	0.1558
5.	Conflict with siblings	1(1.9%)	0	-1.9%	0.1558
II	Control group				
1.	Conflict with friends	0	0	0.0	-
2.	Conflict with self	45(83.3%)	45(83.3%)	0.0	-
3.	Conflict in school	1(1.9%)	0	-1.9%	0.1558
4.	Conflict with parents	0	0	0.0	-
5.	Conflict with siblings	0	1(1.9%)	-1.9%	0.1558

Adolescence is crucial for many aspects of developing self and identity, including commitments, personal goals, motivations, and psychosocial well-being (Becht et al, 2016). During adolescence, youth seek autonomy, particularly from parents, along with increased commitments to social aspects of identity and greater needs for connection with peers (Meeus W et al, 2004). Relatedly, self-evaluations become increasingly differentiated and complex across roles and relationships (Harter S ,2012). Adolescents also frequently report greater self-consciousness, and are more concerned with and interested in others' perceptions of self (Pfeifer JH et al, 2009). The above table indicates that 88.9% of respondents from the experimental group were able to identify the right type of conflict before intervention, but after the intervention most of them i.e 98.1% of the respondents were able to identify the right type of conflict. Responses of the control group respondents remained the same. This indicates that the intervention has had an effect on the respondents from the experimental group.

table 3b: adolescents conflict resolution styles

Sl.No	Conflict styles	resolution	Pre-assessment	Post-assessment	% change	P value
I	Experimental group					
1.	WIN-WIN		27(50.0%)	37(68.5%)	18.5%	0.106
2.	WIN-LOSE/LOSE-WIN		16(29.6%)	17(31.5%)	1.9%	0.4296
3.	LOSE-LOSE		11(20.4%)	0	-20.4%	<0.001**
II	Control group					
1.	WIN-WIN		30(65.2%)	29(63.0%)	-2.2%	0.443
2.	WIN-LOSE/LOSE-WIN		15(32.6%)	15(32.6%)	0.0%	-
3.	LOSE-LOSE		1(2.2%)	2(4.3%)	2.2%	0.273

It can be observed from the table that a majority of the respondents from the experimental group chose a win-win strategy in the simulated conflict with self-situation, and after the intervention a 3.7% difference is observed, while no such difference is observed for the control group.

The table shows that in the pre-assessment phase 50% of the respondents from experimental group opted for win-win conflict resolution in conflict with self, whereas after the intervention 68.5% opted for a win-win conflict resolution. A decrease is observed for the control group, indicating that adolescents need to be taught win-win conflict resolution styles.

It was hypothesized nurturing the development of conflict resolution skills in adolescents will not help them in resolving conflict with self. Data obtained from tables 3A and 3B contradict his assumption. Hence it can be concluded that nurturing the development of conflict resolution skills in adolescents will help them in resolving conflict with self.

VI. CONCLUSION:

Adolescents is a very crucial stage of development. It is a period of 'storm and stress', as stated by Stanley Hall. Adolescents are going through numerous changes, which requires empathy and constant support from others around. Adolescents display immature thinking characteristics, according to Elkind, which leads to them not being able to take the right decisions nor handle their conflicts that they face about themselves, working towards identity, body image issues in a mature manner. This in turn leads to poor mental health. According to WHO, globally, it is estimated that 1 in 7 (14%) 10-19 year-olds experience mental health conditions, yet these remain largely unrecognized and untreated. Hence, this study concludes that adolescents need to be empowered with skills for identifying, understanding and resolving conflict with self for positive mental health.

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